

Association of IL-1 β gene promoter polymorphisms and serum levels with etanercept response in Iraqi patients with moderate to severe psoriasis

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Abstract

Psoriasis, a chronic inflammatory dermatological condition, exhibits heterogeneous responses to anti-TNF therapies such as etanercept (ETN), underscoring the need for predictive biomarkers. This study investigated the association of interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) gene promoter polymorphisms (rs1143623 C/G, rs752338864 C/G, and rs1143627 C/T) with ETN efficacy in 80 Iraqi patients with moderate to severe plaque psoriasis. Patients were categorized according to treatment response: responders achieved $\geq 75\%$ reduction in the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI), whereas non-responders demonstrated $\leq 50\%$ reduction. Post-treatment serum IL-1 β levels were significantly higher in non-responders (50.35 ± 15.81 pg/mL) compared to responders (35.38 ± 10.35 pg/mL; $p = 0.001$). Genotyping revealed that the rs752338864 CC genotype was exclusively present in responders (25% vs 0% in non-responders; $p = 0.001$) and showed a strong inverse correlation with non-responder status ($\phi = -0.342$; $p = 0.003$), as well as a greater reduction in PASI score ($p = 0.01$). Logistic regression further identified serum IL-1 β concentration as an independent predictor of non-response (OR = 1.11; $p = 0.0115$). In contrast, the other investigated SNPs (rs1143623 C/G and rs1143627 C/T) showed no significant association with treatment response. These findings suggest that the rs752338864 CC genotype may indicate a positive response, whereas increased IL-1 β levels could reflect resistance to therapy. Overall, this study sheds new light on psoriasis pharmacogenetics and demonstrates the potential for incorporating genetic and biomarker assessments into individualized treatment strategies.

Keywords

etanercept, gene polymorphism, IL-1 β , psoriasis, serum levels, treatment response

Introduction

Research on the genetic polymorphism of interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) and its influence on the response to anti-tumor necrosis factor (anti-TNF) therapy in psoriasis has be-

come a critical field of study owing to the disease's intricate immunopathogenesis and the inconsistent effectiveness of biologic treatments (Chhabra et al. 2022). Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory dermatological condition. It is frequent in young adults, who are often uncomfortable with

the visible, sore, and scaly plaques and suffer from them in terms of their quality of life (Abdulridha et al. 2020; Armstrong et al. 2023). Psoriasis impacts 2–4% of the population and is distinguished by immune dysregulation involving cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-17, which promote keratinocyte hyperproliferation and systemic inflammation (Berna-Rico et al. 2023; Puşcaş et al. 2023).

Treatment outcomes have improved since the introduction of anti-TNF agents such as adalimumab, infliximab, and etanercept; however, a substantial number of patients experience primary or secondary nonresponse (Zaba et al. 2009; Loft et al. 2018).

Etanercept (ETN), a TNF- α inhibitor, is effective in treating psoriasis by modulating inflammation and immune response. However, some patients do not respond adequately (Li et al. 2023), necessitating a change in treatment. This trial-and-error approach leads to suboptimal patient care and increased healthcare costs, highlighting the need for precise, individualized treatment selection. Pharmacogenetics offers a promising solution, though research on the interplay between genetics and biologics in psoriasis remains limited compared to inflammatory bowel disease and rheumatoid arthritis (Prieto-Pérez et al. 2013).

IL-1 β , situated in the 2q14.1 region of chromosome 2, is implicated in the pathophysiology of psoriasis and encodes a protein essential for the initiation of the acute-phase response (Nicklin et al. 2002). The IL1B cytokine stimulates prostaglandin synthesis, neutrophil recruitment and activation, T-cell activation and cytokine production, and B-cell activation and antibody production, and it facilitates the differentiation of T-helper 17 (Th17) cells while also collaborating with IL-12 to induce IFN synthesis from Th1 cells (Tominaga et al. 2000). IL1B is an exceptionally potent pro-inflammatory cytokine, and potential genetic variations may significantly modulate the efficacy of anti-TNF therapies or cytokine inhibitors.

Pharmacogenomic and pharmacogenetic research aims to use genetic insights to create personalized treatment plans that are both more effective and safer (Ventola 2013). Recent studies, including several in Iraq, have explored the link between genetic polymorphisms—specifically single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in genes such as TNF and interleukins (ILs)—and the response to biological drugs (Khudhur et al. 2022; Mohammed et al. 2022a, 2022b, 2023a, 2023b; Alhilali and Mohammed 2024). However, no previous research has specifically examined the impact of the rs752338864 C/G polymorphism on etanercept response in psoriasis patients, nor have any empirical studies in Iraq investigated how SNPs in the IL-1 β promoter region affect etanercept outcomes in this specific patient population. Therefore, this study

was designed to investigate whether SNPs in the IL-1 β gene promoter at positions rs1143623 C/G, rs752338864 C/G, and rs1143627 C/T influence the effectiveness of etanercept in a cohort of Iraqi psoriasis patients.

Method

This research is part of a thorough observational cross-sectional study conducted from April 2024 to February 2025. The study involved a cohort of 80 Iraqi patients diagnosed with moderate to severe psoriasis. The participants were selected from the Centre of Dermatology and Venereology at Baghdad Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq. This organization provides medical services to diverse populations across Iraq, including rural, urban, and inner-city regions in several governorates. The Scientific and Ethical Committee of the College of Pharmacy at the University of Baghdad and the Dermatology and Venereology Centre at Baghdad Teaching Hospital issued ethical approval (No. RECO-62024R) on 3 April 2024. Furthermore, written consent was obtained from all participants.

Patients' selection

Ninety-three patients with moderate to severe psoriasis treated with ETN as monotherapy for at least 6 months met the inclusion criteria. However, only eighty-five patients agreed to participate in the study, and eighty ultimately met the requirements; five were excluded due to missing data. Participants were required to be at least 18 years old with a confirmed diagnosis of moderate to severe plaque psoriasis, defined as a PASI score greater than 10 (Mrowietz et al. 2011; Daudén et al. 2016). They had to have been on a consistent dose of 50 mg twice weekly for 3 months, followed by 50 mg once weekly, and have completed a minimum total treatment duration of six continuous months before assessment. The PASI score was calculated as follows:

Patient PASI = [(0.1 • (EH+ IH+ DH) • AH) + (0.2 • (EUL+IUL+DUL) • AU) + (0.3 • (ET+IT+DT) • AT) + (0.4 • (ELL+ILL+DLL) • AL)] (Berth-Jones et al. 2006). The study excluded individuals who had been on ETN for less than 6 months, those using other biologic medications, or those receiving any systemic non-biologic immune-modulating agent (e.g., methotrexate, cyclosporine, or oral steroids) concurrently with etanercept. Patients with concurrent skin conditions or with psoriasis types other than plaque psoriasis were also excluded. In addition, patients taking medications known to worsen psoriasis—such as beta-blockers, antimalarials, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, lithium, or tetracycline—were excluded (Table 1).

Table 1. Proposed mechanisms for psoriasis exacerbation by excluded drug classes (Kim and Del Rosso 2010).

Drug class	Example agents	Proposed mechanism of psoriasis exacerbation
Beta-blockers	Propranolol	Reduces cAMP levels; promotes keratinocyte hyperproliferation and T-cell activation.
Antimalarial Agents	Hydroxychloroquine	Triggers the release of inflammatory mediators; increases IL-1 β and TNF- α production.
NSAIDs	Indomethacin	Interferes with arachidonic acid metabolism; leads to an imbalance in inflammatory leukotrienes.
Lithium	Lithium Carbonate	Disrupts inositol metabolism; alters T-cell-mediated inflammation and neutrophil function.
Tetracyclines	Minocycline	May induce photosensitivity (Koeber effect) or lichenoid reactions that mimic or trigger psoriasis.

Patient classification

The patients were divided into two groups based on their response to etanercept. Treatment response was evaluated using the change in the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (Δ PASI), which represents the difference between the PASI score during treatment and the PASI score at baseline.

Responders: This group included 40 patients who showed a clinical response to etanercept, defined as a decrease of $\geq 75\%$ in their PASI score. The non-responder group also consisted of 40 patients, but they showed no response to treatment, defined as a $\leq 50\%$ reduction in their PASI score (Vasilopoulos et al. 2012; Daudén et al. 2016).

Single-nucleotide polymorphism selection

The selection of the three specific SNPs (rs1143623 C/G, rs752338864 C/G, and rs1143627 C/T) was based on their role in the promoter pathway. Both rs1143623 C/G and rs1143627 C/T are promoter region SNPs in *IL1B* previously associated with altered IL-1 β expression and inflammatory phenotypes in published studies (AWilkins et al. 2005; Chen et al. 2006; Ponomarenko et al. 2015). The rs752338864 SNP was included exploratorily due to its close physical proximity to other known functional sites and technical feasibility (co-amplification with rs1143623). We hypothesized that its proximity indicated rs752338864 might act as a surrogate genetic marker for an uncharacterized functional variant in linkage disequilibrium (LD) with the established SNPs. LD analysis was subsequently performed to confirm this genetic correlation.

Collection and processing of samples

Five milliliters of venous blood were collected from the forearm vein of each participant. Subsequently, 2 mL of the collected blood sample were placed into an ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tube for DNA extraction and analysis. The remaining 3 mL were placed in a gel tube and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm. The isolated serum was quantified for IL-1 β using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method. The serum IL-1 β level was determined using an ELISA kit provided by Wuhan Feiyue Biotechnology (Wuhan, China; catalog no. FY-EH1444). This assay utilized a quantitative sandwich enzyme immunoassay methodology (Shah and Maghsoudlou 2016).

Genotyping

Genomic deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) was isolated from peripheral blood leukocytes (cryopreserved EDTA blood specimens) using the EasyPure Blood Genomic DNA Kit (TransGen Biotech, China; catalog no. EE121). The concentration of DNA samples demonstrating acceptable integrity was assessed using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped with computerized software for control and data recording, with an elution buffer used as a blank solution. Two microliters of purified

DNA were introduced into the NanoDrop to ascertain the concentration in ng/ μ L, which ranged from 31 to 54 ng/ μ L. The NanoDrop spectrophotometer was employed to assess DNA purity by measuring the sample's absorbance at two wavelengths—260 and 280 nm. The A260/A280 ratio ranged from 1.7 to 1.9, indicating high DNA purity.

Primer design and optimization

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) primers were designed using Geneious Prime software, with sequences obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database in FASTA format. The primers were synthesized and lyophilized by Alpha DNA Ltd. (Canada). For rs1143623 and rs752338864, a forward primer (CAGGAGGGCTCAGTGTAGG) and a reverse primer (AACACCCCTCCTTTGCCTCTT), both 20 bp long, were designed with a product size of 806 bp. For rs1143627, a forward primer (CCCTTCCATGAACCAGAGAA) and a reverse primer (GGAGCAGAGGCTTTGACACT), also 20 bp long, were designed with a product size of 515 bp.

A stock solution of each primer was prepared by dissolving lyophilized primers in nuclease-free water to a concentration of 100 pmol/ μ L. This stock was stored at -23°C . A working solution was then made by diluting 10 μ L of the stock with 90 μ L of nuclease-free water, resulting in a final concentration of 10 pmol/ μ L for use in experiments. To determine the most efficient conditions for amplification, the annealing temperature was optimized by testing 54°C , 56°C , and 58°C . The optimal temperature, 58°C , consistently produced distinct and well-defined bands on an agarose gel and was therefore used for all subsequent experiments.

PCR amplification and sequencing protocol

PCR amplifications were performed in a total volume of 25 μ L per reaction using the following components: 12.5 μ L of EasyTaq[®] PCR SuperMix, 1 μ L each of the 10 pmol forward and reverse primers, 4 μ L of template DNA, and 6.5 μ L of nuclease-free water. The reactions were briefly centrifuged to ensure that all components were thoroughly mixed before being placed in a QIAamplifier 96 thermocycler. The cycling protocol began with an initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation (94°C for 30 seconds), annealing (58°C for 30 seconds), and extension (72°C for 30 seconds). The process concluded with a final extension at 72°C for 5 minutes. The resulting PCR products were sent to MacroGen Corporation (Seoul, South Korea) for Sanger sequencing using an ABI3730XL automated DNA sequencer. The sequences were subsequently analyzed with Geneious Prime software and compared to the standard IL-1 β gene sequence available in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) GenBank database (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). The resulting sequences were then inserted into the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) program to match them with sequences found in NCBI.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS for Windows, version 29.0. Continuous variables were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation, whereas allele and genotype data were represented as frequencies and percentages. The Shapiro–Wilk test was employed to assess the normality of data distribution. An unpaired t-test was used to evaluate demographic characteristics and parameters between responder and non-responder groups for normally distributed data. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to assess differences among the means of more than two groups, with post hoc analysis conducted upon the detection of a significant difference.

Proportional differences between groups were evaluated using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, the latter being applied for 2×2 comparisons with expected values less than five. The association between each genotype and the likelihood of non-responsiveness was assessed using the Phi correlation coefficient. Binary logistic regression analysis was employed to evaluate the correlation between IL-1 β levels and the probability of being a non-responder. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05 . A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was constructed to evaluate the validity of IL-1 β levels as a predictor of response to etanercept. Diagnostic accuracy was further assessed by calculating the area under the curve (AUC), along with sensitivity and specificity. Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis between IL-1 β SNPs was performed using Haploview software to determine the pairwise D' and r^2 values, confirming the genetic correlation within this gene block.

Result

Demographic data and clinical characteristics of the study groups.

Demographic and clinical characteristics were compared between responders and non-responders. As shown in Table 2, there were no statistically significant differences in baseline characteristics such as age, gender, BMI, disease duration, or comorbidities. After 6 months of treatment, the non-responder group showed significantly higher IL-1 β levels compared to the responder group ($p = 0.001$).

Consistent with the treatment outcome, statistically significant differences were also observed in disease severity. The responder group showed a marked improvement, with significantly lower mean Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) scores (2.04 ± 0.989) and Body Surface Area (BSA) scores (2.89 ± 0.908) after 6 months of treatment. In contrast, the non-responder group had significantly higher mean PASI scores (13.68 ± 3.803 ; $p = 0.01$) and BSA scores (22.06 ± 6.916 ; $p = 0.01$) at the 6-month mark.

Table 2. Demographic data and clinical characteristics of the study groups.

Category		Responders group n = 40	Non-responders group n = 40	P-Value
Age (years)		38.80 \pm 9.40	41.05 \pm 13.12	0.381 ^a
Gender	Male n (%)	21 (52.5%)	26 (65%)	0.2 ^b
	Female n (%)	19 (47.5%)	14 (35%)	
Family history	Yes n (%)	18 (45%)	25 (62.5%)	0.1 ^b
	No n (%)	22 (55%)	15 (37.5%)	
BMI		29.21 \pm 5.074	31.73 \pm 7.157	0.07 ^a
Disease duration (years)		13.20 \pm 4.081	15.10 \pm 5.038	0.3 ^a
IL-1 β (pg/mL)		35.38 \pm 10.35	50.35 \pm 15.81	0.001 ^{* a}
Baseline PASI		19.87 \pm 5.469	19.35 \pm 4.573	0.8 ^a
PASI after 6 months		2.04 \pm 0.989	13.68 \pm 3.803	0.01 ^{* a}
Baseline BSA		29.37 \pm 8.678	30.88 \pm 7.26	0.6 ^a
BSA after 6 months		2.89 \pm 0.908	22.06 \pm 6.916	0.01 ^{* a}
comorbidities	Diabetes n (%)	2 (5)	7 (17.5)	0.15 ^c
	Hypertension n (%)	3 (7.5)	9 (22.5)	0.11 ^c
	Nail psoriasis n (%)	5 (12)	11 (27)	0.09 ^b

Results are presented as means \pm standard deviation or frequency (%). TNF- α : tumor necrosis factor alpha. PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index. BSA: Body Surface Area. a: Independent two-sample t-test. b: Chi-square test. c: Fisher's exact test. *: Significant differences.

Prevalence of genotype polymorphism

Analysis of the three SNPs revealed distinct patterns in genotype and allele frequencies. For rs1143623, the GG genotype was the most common (38.75%). The G allele was more prevalent, with a frequency of 54.38% compared to the C allele's 45.63%.

For both rs752338864 and rs1143627, the heterozygous genotype was the most frequent. The CG genotype of rs752338864 was found in 62.5% of patients, and its G allele was more common (56.25%). Similarly, the CT genotype of rs1143627 was the most prevalent (48.75%). However, unlike the other SNPs, the allele frequencies for rs1143627 were nearly equal, with the C allele at 50.63% and the T allele at 49.37% (Table 3).

Table 3. Genotypes and allele frequencies of IL-1 β gene polymorphisms in psoriasis patients. N = 80 patients.

Genotypes		CC+	CG	GG
rs1143623 C/G	Genetic variant			
	No. (%)	24 (30)	25 (31.25)	31 (38.75)
	Allele	C	G	
rs752338864 C/G	Genetic variant	CC+	CG	GG
	No. (%)	10 (12.5)	50 (62.5)	20 (25)
	Allele	C	G	
rs1143627 C/T	Genetic variant	CC+	CT	TT
	No. (%)	21 (26.25)	39 (48.75)	20 (25)
	Allele	C	T	
	No. (%)	81 (50.63)	79 (49.37)	

Regarding the difference in genotype and allele frequencies, Table 4 shows that only rs752338864 exhibited a significant association with treatment response. The homozygous CC genotype was significantly more common in the responder group (25%) than in the non-responder group (0%), a highly significant difference ($p = 0.001$). The C allele for the same SNP also showed a trend toward significance

($p = 0.056$), with a higher frequency in responders (51%) compared to non-responders (36.25%). In contrast, no significant differences were observed between the two groups for either of the other two SNPs, rs1143623 or rs1143627.

Table 4. Difference in genotype frequencies of IL-1 β gene polymorphisms between responders and non-responders.

Genotypes	Responders group (n = 40) No. (%)	Non-responders' group (n = 40) No. (%)	P-Value	
rs1143623 C/G	CC+	12 (30)	1.0	
	CG	12 (30)	0.8	
	GG	16 (40)	0.8	
	C	36 (45)	0.8	
	G	44 (55)	43 (53.75)	
rs752338864 C/G	CC+	10 (25)	0.001*	
	CG	21 (52.5)	29 (72.5)	
	GG	9 (22.5)	11 (27.5)	
	C	41 (51)	29 (36.25)	
	G	39 (49)	51 (63.75)	
rs1143627 C/T	CC+	13 (32.5%)	8 (20%)	0.2
	CT	17 (42.5%)	22 (55%)	0.3
	TT	10 (25%)	10 (25%)	1.0
	C	43 (53.75%)	38 (47.5%)	0.4
	T	37 (46.25%)	42 (52.5%)	

Association between genotypes and the probability of being a non-responder

As shown in Table 5, only the CC genotype of the rs752338864 genetic variant demonstrated a significant association with non-responder status ($p = 0.003$). The negative phi coefficient ($\phi = -0.342$) indicates that this genotype is inversely correlated with being a non-responder, suggesting a protective effect or a higher likelihood of being a treatment responder. In contrast, none of the other genotypes showed a statistically significant association.

Table 5. Phi coefficient and statistical association between each genotype and non-responder status among study participants.

SNP	Genotype	Phi coefficient	P. Value
rs1143623	CC+	0	1
rs1143623	CG	0.028	0.812
rs1143623	GG	0	1
rs752338864	CC+	-0.342	0.003*
rs752338864	CG	0.187	0.111
rs752338864	GG	0.119	0.309
rs1143627	CC+	0.136	0.247
rs1143627	CT	0.121	0.302
rs1143627	TT	0.055	0.636

The correlations between the genotypes and the difference in the PASI score

Analysis of the data in Table 6 revealed a significant association ($p = 0.01$) between a patient's genotype for the rs752338864 SNP and their change in PASI score (Δ PASI). Specifically, individuals with the CC genotype demonstrated the most substantial improvement, with a mean Δ PASI of -19.08 . A post hoc test confirmed this result, showing that the improvement for the CC genotype was significantly better than for both the CG (mean Δ PASI = -11.04) and GG (mean Δ PASI = -8.42) genotypes. In contrast, the other two SNPs, rs1143623

Table 6. Association of the change in PASI over six months between different genotypes in the IL-1 β gene polymorphism.

SNPs	Genotype	Δ PASI		P-value
		Mean	Standard deviation	
rs1143623 C/G	CC	-13.91	6.08	0.3
	CG	-9.65	4.59	
	GG	-11.31	5.28	
rs752338864 C/G	CC	-19.08 a	8.07	0.01*
	CG	-11.04 b	5.75	
	GG	-8.42 b	4.53	
rs1143627 C/T	CC	-11.59	5.45	0.7
	GT	-12.41	6.78	
	TT	-10.36	4.39	

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD. Statistical analyses were performed by ANOVA followed by a post hoc test (Duncan's test) for multiple comparisons. ANOVA significance test (two-tailed). a and b: Different letters indicate a significant difference. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different. SD: standard deviation.

($p = 0.3$) and rs1143627 ($p = 0.7$), did not show a significant relationship with the change in PASI score.

Linkage disequilibrium among the polymorphisms of the IL1- β

Linkage disequilibrium analysis confirmed a strong genetic correlation between the investigated *IL1B* polymorphisms (Fig. 1). Specifically, rs752338864 showed an almost complete genetic relationship with the established rs1143627, with values of $D' = 0.96$ and $r^2 = 0.71$. This strong LD confirms that rs752338864 is highly linked to the functional promoter region and can be considered a reliable surrogate genetic marker in this cohort.

Comparison of serum IL-1 β concentrations across genotypes in psoriatic patients

According to Table 7, the rs752338864 C/G variant showed a significant overall difference across genotypes ($p = 0.03$), with a post hoc test highlighting a specific difference between the CC and CG genotypes. The data from Table 8 further clarify this relationship by linking specific genotypes to treatment response. Patients who did not respond to treatment had significantly higher IL-1 β levels compared to those who did, and this pattern was consistently observed across several genotypes. These findings suggest that certain genotypes are associated with elevated IL-1 β levels and a poor response to treatment.

Table 7. IL-1 β level in different genotypes.

SNPs	Genetic variant	CC+	CG	GG	P-Value
rs1143623 C/G	IL-1 β	42.83 \pm 15.39	45.64 \pm 24.63	39.03 \pm 11.06	0.37
	Genetic variant	CC+	CG	GG	
rs752338864 C/G	IL-1 β	28.80 \pm 7.86 a	45.36 \pm 15.76 b	43.65 \pm 24.45	0.03*
	Genetic variant	CC+	CT	TT	
rs1143627 C/T	IL-1 β	36.76 \pm 11.68	44.36 \pm 18.41	46.35 \pm 22.56	0.19

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD. Statistical analyses were performed by ANOVA followed by a post hoc test (Duncan's test) for multiple comparisons. ANOVA significance test (two-tailed). a and b: Indicate a significant difference between genotypes.

Figure 1. The values of D' and r^2 among polymorphisms of the IL-1 β gene in the studied groups. Abbreviations: D' , linkage disequilibrium; r^2 , correlation factor.

Table 8. Comparison of serum IL-1 β concentrations across genotypes in psoriatic patients classified by treatment response.

		Responder (N = 40)		Non-responder (N = 40)		P-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
rs1143623 C/G	CC	33.50	10.48	51.92	15.53	0.002*
	CG	33.00	8.39	58.23	19.94	0.01*
	GG	38.56	13.59	41.57	10.06	0.5
rs752338864 C/G	CC	28.80	7.86	0.0	0.0	-
	CG	37.67	13.24	50.93	15.27	0.002*
	GG	37.33	6.96	48.82	12.12	0.3
rs1143627 C/T	CC	31.46	7.85	45.38	12.13	0.005*
	CT	33.76	11.27	52.55	18.86	0.001*
	TT	43.20	12.46	49.50	19.95	0.5

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD. An unpaired t-test was performed for statistical analysis.

Receiver operating characteristic curve for post-treatment IL-1 β concentration

Based on the analysis presented in Fig. 2, the ROC curve for serum IL-1 β showed a moderate ability to distinguish between responders and non-responders. The area under the curve (AUC) was 0.75, a statistically significant value ($p < 0.001$). At the optimal cut-off value of 42.5, the test's performance was characterized by a sensitivity of 65% and a specificity of 82%.

Association between IL-1 β and the likelihood of being a non-responder

Based on the logistic regression analysis in Table 9, serum IL-1 β concentration was identified as a significant predictor of non-response ($p = 0.0115$). The coefficient (β) was +0.1052, and the odds ratio (OR) was approximately 1.11, indicating that for every one-unit increase in IL-1 β concentration, the odds of a patient being a non-responder increase by 11%.

Figure 2. Receiver operating characteristic curve for post-treatment IL-1 β concentration.

Table 9. Logistic regression of IL-1 β as a predictor of non-response.

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value	OR	95% CI
Intercept (const)	-13.57	0.0002	1.111	[-20.67, -6.47]
IL-1 β concentration	+0.1052	0.0115		[0.0236-0.1867]

Discussion

Etanercept is a valuable treatment option for moderate to severe plaque psoriasis. Compared to other systemic treatments for psoriasis, it has high efficacy, a favorable benefit-to-side-effect ratio, and long-term safety (Dhaher and Mohammed 2024). Nevertheless, variability in treatment response remains a significant challenge. Polymorphisms in genes that directly or indirectly interact with drug action may influence therapeutic outcomes (Vašků et al. 2020). Pharmacogenetics, therefore, has emerged as

a promising field for identifying biomarkers that predict responsiveness to TNF- α inhibitors. Numerous polymorphisms have been investigated in relation to response to TNF- α inhibitors (Murdaca et al. 2014). The present study focused on three IL-1 β promoter polymorphisms and their potential impact on resistance to etanercept.

Regarding the demographic characteristics, the results of the study revealed that the mean age and duration of psoriasis were comparable to those reported in previous Iraqi studies on psoriasis patients (Naif 2015; Abdulridha et al. 2020). This similarity suggests that our cohort is representative of the broader Iraqi psoriasis population. Additionally, a comparable duration of disease indicates that our patients were not restricted to either newly diagnosed or chronic cases, which reduces selection bias. This demographic alignment improves the external validity of our findings and allows for more reliable comparisons with local and international study cohorts.

Previous studies conducted in Iraq have investigated the prevalence of the genetic variant rs1143627 C/T in keratoconus disease, recurrent tonsillitis, and multiple sclerosis (Ali and Kazaz 2018; Dhumad 2023; Mohammed and Fadhil 2024). However, no study has assessed its role in psoriasis, nor have rs1143623 C/G or rs752338864 C/G been investigated in any disease within Iraq. Thus, this study is the first to evaluate these three SNPs in Iraqi psoriasis patients.

Globally, IL-1 β polymorphisms have been associated with anti-TNF response in several immune-mediated disorders. For instance, rs1143634 was associated with infliximab response in inflammatory bowel disease. (Lacruz-Guzmán et al. 2013) and with anti-TNF response in juvenile idiopathic arthritis (Cimaz et al. 2007). Similarly, rs1143623 and rs1143627 were studied in Danish psoriasis patients treated with anti-TNF agents, including ETN (Loft et al. 2018). The findings of these studies indicate that variations in the IL-1 β gene warrant further investigation to assess their influence on the outcomes of biological therapies.

This study provides the first evidence that the rs752338864 CC genotype in the *IL1B* gene is strongly related to a good response to etanercept. All CC carriers showed significant PASI reduction, and none were classified as non-responders ($p = 0.001$). This was supported by phi correlation ($\phi = -0.342$, $p = 0.003$), identifying CC as a protective factor against treatment failure. To our knowledge, this is the first study worldwide to analyze the rs752338864 C/G polymorphism in the *IL1B* gene. Functionally, rs752338864 is located in the *IL1B* promoter, where single-nucleotide variations can alter transcription factor binding and transcriptional expression, as demonstrated for neighboring variants rs1143623 and rs1143627, which modify transcription factor occupancy and reporter activity, thereby regulating IL-1 β expression (Landvik et al. 2012; Piber et al. 2020). Given IL-1 β 's established role in amplifying Th17-axis inflammation and keratinocyte activation in psoriasis, diminished pro-

motor activity would likely enhance etanercept efficacy, whereas increased activity would sustain inflammation and counteract TNF inhibition (Cai et al. 2019). The observed association of rs752338864 with etanercept response is strongly supported by linkage disequilibrium analysis, which confirmed a high genetic correlation ($D' = 0.96$; $r^2 = 0.71$) between rs752338864 and the established functional polymorphism rs1143627. This tight genetic linkage reinforces the conclusion that the effect of rs752338864 reflects the influence of the *IL1B* promoter region on etanercept efficacy.

The absence of prior studies limited our ability to compare our results directly; however, the present data highlight the potential importance of this polymorphism and underscore the need for replication in larger, ethnically diverse cohorts. Findings of such studies may vary between populations because of pharmacogenetic, racial, and ethnic differences resulting from variation in allele frequencies (Bachtiar and Lee 2013).

For rs1143623, the mutant homozygous GG genotype was predominant in our cohort, followed by the CG and CC genotypes. The G allele was predominant (>50%). Comparable patterns have been documented in Swedish individuals with bipolar disorder (Strenn et al. 2021) and in Chinese individuals with colorectal cancer (Qian et al. 2018). However, other populations, such as Southwest Chinese women with gestational diabetes, reported the heterozygous CG genotype as predominant (Liu et al. 2020). Despite these population-level differences, our investigation showed no significant associations between genotype or allele frequencies, PASI reduction, and phi correlation. By contrast, a study on Danish psoriasis patients (Loft et al. 2018) indicated that the variant alleles of rs1143623 (CG + GG) genotypes correlated with non-responsiveness to anti-TNF agents, whereas Spanish cohorts reported better outcomes (Loras et al. 2024). These disparities may stem from population-level variation, as allele frequencies and linkage disequilibrium patterns of *IL1B* variants can differ considerably between ethnic groups (Mwantembe et al. 2001; Manchanda et al. 2005), thus modifying the functional impact of rs1143623. Methodological differences in study design may also contribute; for example, our investigation focused on etanercept monotherapy, whereas other studies evaluated anti-TNF drugs collectively. This distinction is critical, as anti-TNF medications are not functionally identical. Etanercept, a soluble TNF receptor-Fc fusion protein, exhibits a distinct mechanism of action against membrane-bound TNF compared with monoclonal antibodies such as infliximab or adalimumab. Such pharmacological differences may partly explain inconsistent genotype–response associations across studies (Mitoma et al. 2008; Licastro et al. 2009; Tichy et al. 2023).

The rs1143627 variant showed the C/T genotype as the most prevalent in our cohort (49.75%), with nearly equal C (50.63%) and T (49.37%) allele frequencies. This aligns with findings from other regional studies in Iraqi patients with recurrent tonsillitis (Mohammed and Fadhil 2024),

Egyptian individuals with autism spectrum disorders (Saad et al. 2020), and Iranian patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (Mohammadoo-Khorasani et al. 2016). In contrast, a keratoconus disease study in Iraq reported that the TT genotype was most frequent (60%), with a T allele frequency of 72% (Ali and Kazaz 2018). These variations in rs1143627 genotype frequencies may be attributed to the specific diseases studied, as certain genotypes may become more prevalent due to their association with particular diseases (Liu 2018). In terms of ETN response, rs1143627 showed no significant associations with genotype, allele distribution, PASI improvement, or phi correlation. However, Loft et al. found that the variant alleles of rs1143627 were linked to non-response when considering PASI score reduction after 3 months of treatment in Danish psoriasis patients (Loft et al. 2018). Importantly, rs1143627 is located in the TATA-proximal region and has established functional effects on transcription (Ponomarenko et al. 2015). Hence, null findings in our study do not exclude modest effects that necessitate larger, ancestry-diverse cohorts for confirmation. Given that Loft et al.'s is the only study addressing rs1143627 in the context of anti-TNF response, further empirical validation remains essential before drawing definitive conclusions.

The rs1143623 and rs1143627 polymorphisms in *IL1B* have demonstrated associations with disease susceptibility and treatment response in certain diseases, although these results are not universally applicable. For instance, in rheumatoid arthritis, the rs1143623 polymorphism did not directly correlate with disease severity but may offer a protective effect (Harrison et al. 2008), while both polymorphisms showed no association with acute coronary syndrome, indicating that their influence may be limited or context-dependent (Stegger et al. 2012). These findings suggest that their influence may be limited or context-dependent in psoriasis, and their predictive power remains modest compared to other genetic factors such as *HLA-Cw*06*. The lack of standardized assays and prospective validation studies limits their immediate clinical implementation. Additionally, the influence of epigenetic modifications and environmental factors on IL-1 β expression and treatment response remains underexplored (Berna-Rico et al. 2023). This underscores the necessity of considering genetic, environmental, and demographic factors when evaluating the influence of *IL1B* polymorphisms on disease and treatment outcomes.

The biological effect of the investigated SNPs on *IL1B* expression (Chen et al. 2006) and IL-1 β release (Iacoviello et al. 2005) is well established. In this study, rs752338864 genotypes correlated with significantly different IL-1 β levels, particularly between the CC and CG genotypes. A Danish pharmacogenetic study highlighted the translational significance of *IL1B* promoter variation (Loft et al. 2018), finding that variant alleles at rs1143623 and rs1143627 correlated with elevated IL-1 β production and were associated with non-response to anti-TNF and ustekinumab therapy. Current reviews of psoriasis

pharmacogenetics summarize the same findings and highlight *IL1B* promoter polymorphisms as candidates for predicting anti-TNF outcomes (Muñoz-Aceituno et al. 2020; Membrive Jiménez et al. 2021). Our findings reinforce this, as non-responders displayed elevated blood IL-1 β levels, consistent with the established role of IL-1 β in promoting cutaneous inflammation and treatment resistance in chronic psoriasis (Wu et al. 2014; Bou-Dargham et al. 2017). Together, our findings provide evidence for a functional model in which the rs752338864 CC promoter configuration diminishes IL-1 β -mediated inflammation and increases responsiveness to etanercept, whereas genotypes that permit elevated IL-1 β levels predispose individuals to a non-responsive state. Additionally, elevated post-treatment IL-1 β showed moderate predictive accuracy for ETN non-response (AUC 0.75, optimal cut-off 42.5 pg/mL), suggesting potential utility as a dynamic biomarker.

Beyond genetic susceptibility, this study emphasizes post-treatment IL-1 β levels as a significant predictor of non-response (β coefficient = +0.1052). This supports prior evidence that increased inflammatory markers can predict adverse outcomes in chronic inflammatory diseases (Bou-Dargham et al. 2017; Aggeletopoulou et al. 2024). Thus, monitoring IL-1 β during therapy could provide actionable insights into treatment efficacy. The potential clinical relevance of rs752338864 lies in its high feasibility for implementation; PCR methods are routine, inexpensive, and readily available. However, for this test to justify influencing therapeutic decisions, its predictive accuracy must reach a high threshold (e.g., AUC > 0.85 or high PPV). A major strength of this study is the strict patient selection, which ensured that all participants were receiving etanercept as the sole systemic immune-modulating agent, minimizing confounding factors and strengthening the validity of the observed genetic association.

The study's main limitation is its relatively small sample size, which may have reduced statistical power and led to an underestimation of effect sizes or failure to detect subtle correlations. Additionally, the single-center design limits generalizability to the broader Iraqi psoriasis population, although this center receives patients from all governorates. Finally, the study could not include an extended follow-up period to assess long-term outcomes in specific genotypes due to limited resources and facilities.

Conclusion

This study provides the first evidence that rs752338864 CC is strongly associated with a favorable etanercept response and a reduced likelihood of non-response in Iraqi psoriasis patients, whereas rs1143623 and rs1143627 showed no significant associations. Concurrently, elevated post-treatment IL-1 β levels strongly indicate therapeutic non-responsiveness, reinforcing their role as a dynamic biomarker. These findings underscore the significance of

IL-1 β promoter variants in psoriasis pharmacogenetics; however, validation in larger multicenter and ethnically diverse cohorts remains essential before clinical translation.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors, or donors' representatives: Ethical approval was received from the University of Baghdad, College of Pharmacy Ethical Committee (reference number RECO-62024R; date: 3 April 2024).

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Use of AI

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Author contributions

The first author was mainly responsible for study design, data collection, analysis, and drafting the manuscript. The second author assisted with data collection, analysis, and manuscript editing. The third author provided supervision, guidance, and final review. All authors approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17365705> (reference number 17365705).

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Supplementary material 1

Images of amplification and sequencing of IL1B

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Data type: pdf

Explanation note: Text.

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